

Synthesis of 6-Benzoyl-8-methyl flavonoids

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6-Benzoyl-8-methylflavanones, -flavones and flavonols have been synthesised from 5'-benzoyl-3'-methyl-2'-hydroxychalcone derivatives by the action of dilute ethanolic sulphuric acid, selenium dioxide and alkaline hydrogen peroxide respectively.

In continuation of our study of 2'-hydroxychalcones and related heterocyclic compounds (Amin and Amin, this *Journal*, 1959, 23, 126 and references cited therein), 6-benzoyl-8-methylflavonoid derivatives have been described in the present communication. 5'-Benzoyl-3'-methyl-2'-hydroxychalcones (I) prepared from 5-benzoyl-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone (Amin and Amin, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 469) were isomerised into 6-benzoyl-8-methylflavanones (II) by the action of dilute ethanolic sulphuric acid (Seshadri *et al. Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1954, 39A, 296).

Similarly, the same chalcones have been cyclodehydrogenated by selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol into 6-benzoyl-8-methylflavones (III: X=H) (Mahal *et al. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 866; 1936, 569) and cyclohydroxylated into the corresponding flavonols (III: X=OH) by alkaline hydrogen peroxide (Algar and Flynn, *Proc. Roy. Irish Acad.*, 1934, 42B, 1; *Chem. Abs.*, 1935, 20, 161). Thus, 5'-benzoyl-3'-methyl-2'-hydroxychalcones could be easily converted into the corresponding flavonoids and the presence of—COPh group does not inhibit or retard the various reactions (cf. Joshi and Amin, *Izvestia Acad. Nauk, USSR, Otdel, Khim. Nauk*, 1960, 267).

EXPERIMENTAL

The various 5'-benzoyl-3'-methyl-2'-hydroxychalcones (I), 6-benzoyl-8-methyl flavanones (II), -flavones (III, X=H) and flavonols (III, X=OH) have been prepared by the general procedures, described below, and all the compounds are listed in Tables I to IV. The solvent for crystallisation of each compound is indicated by letter in parenthesis (A, acetic acid and E, ethanol).

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General Procedures

5'-Benzoyl-3'-methyl-2'-hydroxychalkone (I).—A 46% KOH solution (20 c.c.) was added to a homogeneous solution of 5-benzoyl-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone (1 g.) and the aldehyde (0.7 g.) in ethanol (20-30 c.c.) with continuous shaking. The mixture was kept overnight at room temperature (22-26°) after heating for 5-10 minutes on water bath, when the colour changed from yellow to brown. On dilution with ice-water and acidification by HCl (1:1), a yellow solid separated. It was washed with NaHCO₃ solution (5%) and crystallised. It developed characteristic deep red colour with H₂SO₄ (conc). It dissolved in NaOH solution with yellow color and gave reddish brown colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

TABLE I
5'-Benzoyl-3'-methyl-2'-hydroxychalkones (I)

Sr.No.	Substituent (R)	Colour and cryst. form	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Nil	Yellow shining needles (A)	134°	C ₂₃ H ₁₀ O ₃	C : 80.50 H : 5.06	80.70% 5.26
2.	Acetyl of (1)	„ (E)	96°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₄	C : 77.86 H : 5.12	78.12 5.21
3.	3-Hydroxy	Pale yellow needles (A)	166°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₃	C : 76.67 H : 4.94	76.81 5.00
4.	Acetyl of (3)	Colorless needles (E)	109°	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₆	C : 72.98 H : 4.90	73.50 4.98
5.	2-Methoxy	Yellow granules (A)	160°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄	C : 77.34 H : 5.27	77.43 5.38
6.	Acetyl of (5)	Colorless plates (EtOAc).	101°	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₅	C : 75.11 H : 5.25	75.36 5.31
7.	3,4-Dimethoxy	Yellow needles (A)	165°	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₅	C : 74.55 H : 5.38	74.62 5.47
8.	Acetyl of (7)	Pale yellow needles (E)	117°	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₆	C : 72.73 H : 5.30	72.97 5.41
9.	3,4-Methylene-dioxy	Yellow shining needles (A)	191°	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₃	C : 74.38 H : 4.52	74.61 4.66
10.	Acetyl of (9)	Clusters of yellowish needles (E)	147°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₆	C : 72.63 H : 4.57	72.91 4.66
11.	3-Nitro	Green shining needles (A)	175°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₅ N	C : 70.98 H : 4.35	71.31 4.39
12.	Acetyl of (11)	Yellowish needles (E)	143°	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₆ N	C : 69.64 H : 4.42	69.92 4.43
13.	3-Chloro-4-methoxy	Greenish yellow needles (A)	150°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.70	8.73
14.	Acetyl of (13)	Slightly yellow granules (EtOAc)	134°	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₅ Cl	Cl : 7.83	7.91

Note : The compounds No. 1, 5, 7 and 9 are mentioned in the earlier paper (Amin and Amin, *loc. cit.*)

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared by heating a mixture of the chalkone, acetic anhydride and few drops of pyridine. The reaction mixture after dilution with acidulated water gave a solid which was crystallised.

6-Benzoyl-8-methylflavanone (II):—A hot solution of 5'-benzoyl-3'-methyl-2'-hydroxychalkone (0.5g.) in ethanol (30-40 c.c.) was treated with 10% aqueous H₂SO₄ (15-20 c.c.) till a whitish turbidity appeared. Sufficient ethanol (10-15 c.c.) was added to get a clear solution, which was refluxed on a water bath for 25-35 hours. Afterwards, ethanol was removed by distillation and the coloured solid obtained on cooling the residual liquid was crystallised.

TABLE II

6-Benzoyl-8-methylflavanones (II)

Sr. No	Substituent (R')	Colour and cryst. form.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
15.	Nil	Pale shining plates (E)	108°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₃	C : 80.23 H : 5.23	80.70 5.26
16.	3'-Hydroxy	Yellow shining plates (E)	124°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C : 76.57 H : 4.79	76.81 5.00
17.	2'-Methoxy	Pale yellow needles (E)	134°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄	C : 77.09 H : 5.33	77.42 5.38
18.	3', 4'-Dimethoxy	Yellowish granules (E)	127°	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₅	C : 74.51 H : 5.46	74.62 5.47
19.	3',4'-Methylenedioxy	Yellowish brown granules (E)	154°	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₅	C : 74.18 H : 4.65	74.61 4.66
20.	3'-Nitro	Yellowish shining plates (E)	144°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₅ N	C : 70.86 H : 4.37	71.31 4.39
21.	3'-chloro-4'-methoxy	Greyish granules (E)	151°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.82	8.73

6-Benzoyl 8-methylflavone (III, X=H).—Selenium dioxide (0.5 g.) was added to the chalkone (I, 0.5 g.) dissolved in dry isoamyl alcohol (20-25 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed at 150-60° for 18-20 hours (CaCl₂ guard tube). The precipitated selenium was filtered and the filtrate was subjected to the steam distillation to remove isoamyl alcohol. The brownish solid obtained was crystallised.

TABLE III

6-Benzoyl -8-methyl-flavones (III, X=H)

Sr. No.	Substituent (R')	Colour and cryst. form	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
22.	Nil	Colourless granules (E)	183°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₃	C : 80.87 H : 4.63	81.17 4.71
23.	3'-Hydroxy	Yellow granules (A)	240°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C : 77.31 H : 4.37	77.53 4.49
24.	2'-Methoxy	Brownish granules (A)	210°	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄	C : 77.50 H : 4.81	77.84 4.87
25.	3',4'-Dimethoxy.	Yellowish short needles (E)	254°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₅	C : 74.77 H : 4.94	75.00 5.00
26.	3',4'-Methylene-dioxy	Yellowish needles (A)	225°	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₅	C : 74.71 H : 4.14	75.00 4.17
27.	3'-Nitro	Yellowish needles (A)	241°	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ O ₅ N	C : 71.46 H : 3.86	71.68 3.99
28.	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxy	Brownish shining needles (A)	222°	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.64	8.78

6-Benzoyl-8-methylflavonol (III, X=OH).—5% NaOH (20-25c.c.) solution was added to a solution of chalkone (I, 0.4 g.) in ethanol (25 c.c.). The brownish red solution was treated with 16% H₂O₂ (5-7c.c.) after cooling in an ice bath and left for 3-4 hours. A solid began to separate and the colour of the solution slowly changed to yellow. The reaction mixture was then left overnight at room temperature (22-26°). On dilution with ice-cold water and acidification by dilute HCl, a yellow solid separated, which was crystallised. It is soluble in excess of alkali and develops a greenish blue fluorescence with conc. H₂SO₄.

The *acetyl* derivative of flavonol was prepared by the acetic anhydride—pyridine method.

TABLE IV

6-Benzoyl-8-methylflavonols (III, X=OH)

Sr. No.	Substituent (R')	Colour and cryst. form	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
29.	Nil	Yellow granules (A)	247°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	C : 77.34 H : 4.42	77.54 4.49
30.	Acetyl of (29)	Colourless needles (E)	191°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₅	C : 74.99 H : 4.51	75.37 4.53
31.	3-Hydroxy	Greenish short needles (A)	217°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₅	C : 73.87 H : 4.18	74.20 4.27
32.	Acetyl of (31)	Colourless plates (E)	181°	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₇	C : 70.81 H : 4.28	71.04 4.38
33.	2'-Methoxy	Yellowish shining short needles (A)	250°	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₅	C : 74.33 H : 4.62	74.61 4.66
34.	Acetyl of (33)	White slim needles (E)	205°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₆	C : 72.52 H : 4.63	72.91 4.67
35.	3',4'-Dimethoxy	Light yellow needles (A)	233°	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ O ₅	C : 71.90 H : 4.69	72.11 4.81
36.	Acetyl of (35)	Colourless needles (E)	201°	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₇	C : 70.23 H : 4.72	70.73 4.80
37.	3',4'-Methylenedioxy	Yellowish light needles (A)	260°	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₆	C : 71.81 H : 3.93	72.00 4.00
38.	Acetyl of (37)	Discoloured short needles (E)	220°	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ O ₇	C : 70.28 H : 4.01	70.60 4.07
39.	3'-Nitro	Almost colourless granules (A)	190°	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ O ₆ N	C : 68.59 H : 3.70	68.82 3.74
40.	Acetyl of (39)	Pale yellow plates (E)	124°	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ O ₇ N	C : 67.56 H : 3.80	67.72 3.84
41.	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxy	Brownish shining needles (A)	261°	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₅ Cl	Cl : 8.29	8.44
42.	Acetyl of (41)	Colourless thin needles (E)	189°	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ O ₆ Cl	Cl : 7.56	7.69

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